

Gulf Coast Buff-breasted Sandpiper Survey
2018 Protocol and Instructions for Completing Datasheets
V3 -April 12, 2018

1.0 General Information

- **Safety**

- When selecting road-side points to survey, we tried to select only “secondary” roads and purposefully avoided placing points on highways and other busy roads. However, if it is not safe to pull over at the designated point, please move the point to a safer location. See “Moving Points” below.
- Because we tried to locate points only on secondary roads, many points are on small unpaved roads that may not be passable for a variety of reasons (recent rain, etc.). If you cannot access a survey point because the road is not passable, please find an alternate route, or skip the point and go to the next point. Record the Point # and “not surveyed, road not passable” on the datasheet.

- **Moving Points for Safety or Inaccessible Locations (have to get onto private land, etc.)**

- **If you move a point please notify Kammie Kruse (ASAP) or Kelli Stone ASAP** with the new lat/long so she can provide that information to the next observer on that route. You can email or text her a picture of your data sheet (contact information in Section 6 and Appendix 2)
- You can **move the survey point to a new location up to 0.1 mile** under these conditions:
 - If the randomly selected point is an unsafe location (construction, driving speed, etc.), it is OK to move the point to a safe location (beyond construction zone, to nearby side street, etc.). **Record the same Point # and be sure to record the new latitude and longitude for the new location on the Point-Quadrant Habitat datasheet** (≥ 5 decimal places).
 - Add a comment on the datasheet: “moved point for safety – construction” or “moved point safety – high speed road”. These notes will help us keep track of which points should be moved permanently.
 - If the randomly selected point has an obstructed view of the roadside habitat, it is OK to move the point location up to 0.1 miles to increase visibility of roadside habitat. **Record the same Point # and latitude and longitude of new point location on the Point-Quadrant Habitat datasheet** (≥ 5 decimal places).
 - Add a comment on the datasheet: “moved point for access – visual obstruction”. These notes will help us keep track of which points should be moved permanently.
 - If a suitable point cannot be found, skip the point and go to the next one.
 - Record the Point # on the BBSA Detections datasheet and “not surveyed”.
- You can move the point **up to any distance** under these conditions:
 - If you can't access the point because you have to get onto private lands, but it is possible to view the habitat around/near the point from another vantage point (e.g., outside a gate), please move the point to the public road and **record the new latitude and longitude for the new point location (on the Point-Quadrant Habitat datasheet** (≥ 5 decimal places).

- Add a comment on the datasheet: “moved point for access – private road to public road”. These notes will help us keep track of which points should be moved permanently.
 - **Under any of the above conditions, if a suitable point cannot be found, skip the point and go to the next one.** Note on your datasheet that point was skipped and why.
- **Navigating from Point-to-Point**
 - Load the KML file with latitude-longitude for the survey points to your GPS unit or smartphone. See directions from K. Kruse in Appendix 1.
 - The suggested path (roads) in the KML file and PDF map are not important; if there is a better way to get from one survey point to the next, please use it. In some cases, the suggested path may include private roads; please re-route to the most convenient public road.
 - The order in which the points are surveyed is not important. If there is a more convenient order in which to visit the points, please use it – but please be sure to record the correct Point # on your datasheet.
- **Survey Period:** 20 April to about 15 May. Within this sampling period there are four survey periods. The target dates are below and we encourage observers to conduct their survey on the target date or within a window of 3 days after the target date. However, it is more important to collect data than miss survey completely, so if you can’t do the survey within the 3-day window please contact Kelli Stone.
 - **Survey Period #1: 20 April** target date, (window: April 21, 22, 23)
 - **Survey Period #2: 27 April** target date, (window: April 28, 29, 30)
 - **Survey Period #3: 4 May** target date, (window: May 5, 6, 7)
 - **Survey Period #4: 11 May** target date, (window: May 12, 13, 14)
 - **If it is not possible to complete all points in 1 day, you can complete your survey in 2 consecutive days if necessary.**
 - If you cannot survey (or cannot finish all points on) your route for whatever reason (weather, out of time, etc.), please contact K. Stone because there is flexibility in the schedule. We may ask you to complete the route on a day that is convenient for you, or we may find another observer to survey the remaining points.
- **Number of Observers:** Two people are not required but it is often convenient to have a second person to record data. “Observer” and “Recorder” may alternate between points, but please only one person is to detect BBSA per point. Record the initials of observer on the datasheet. The second person should not locate birds for the first observer.
- **Survey Weather and Start Time:**
 - Little/no precipitation.
 - If weather prevents the observer from completing all the points on a route, the route can be completed on another day.
 - Surveys should begin between 7 and 9 am.

2.0 Equipment

- GPS unit (or smart-phone) with latitude-longitude for all survey points on the route (from KML file provide by Kammie Kruse)
 - See directions from K. Kruse (Appendix 1) from accessing KML file on GPS or smartphone
 - Please set your GPS unit to use WGS 84 datum; on datasheets, enter latitude and longitude in decimal degrees with at least 5 decimal places
- Rangefinder

- Extra batteries for GPS and rangefinder
- Binoculars (no minimum magnification; spotting scope is optional)
- Copies of three datasheets: 1) BBSA Detections datasheet, 2) Point-Quadrant Habitat datasheet, and 3) Incidental datasheet
- Clipboard
- PDF map of route (from K. Kruse)
- CSV file with latitude-longitude of survey points
- Field Guide

3.0 Instructions for the BBSA Detections Datasheet

3.1 General Instructions for the BBSA Detections Datasheet

- **Survey Point Center:** Stand at a location where you can view roadside habitat. This is the center of the point and you will measure distance data from this point. Be sure to measure distances from this point – do not walk up and down the road. Be sure to scan for BBSA and record bird detections and distances before recording habitat data.
- **Record distance to, and micro-habitat data for every single BBSA and flocks of BBSA.** The definition of “flock” is subjective and it is difficult to give guidance on determining whether birds are in a flock or not. A flock is a group of birds in close association and using the same microhabitat (see below). A flock is also a group of birds in close enough proximity to each other that if you detected one bird in the group you were certain to detect the others.
- **Birds close to the point center:** As soon as you arrive at the point, scan the roadside habitat within 50 m of the point center and measure distance with a rangefinder (even at close range) to any birds or flocks before they move in response to the observer. If you walk up to the point from a safe parking location, note the location of all birds and flocks at close range. If you are able to park at the designated location for the survey point and will stand beside the vehicle, check the area around the vehicle for birds before, or immediately after, exiting the vehicle if possible. Use landmarks in the field if necessary to note the locations of birds before they move.
- **Establishing quadrants around the survey point:** The area around the survey point is visually divided into quadrants (right front, right rear, left front, and left rear) to facilitate data collection and habitat mapping. The road itself is the axis to determine “left” and “right”. Use the suggested roadway and direction of travel to the survey point (found in the KML file and PDF map) to determine “front” and “rear”. Face in the direction of the suggested roadway to the point and then you can visualize “left, right, front, and rear.”
- **Flyovers:** BBSA flying over the survey point, or into the surveyed area after the start of the survey, should be documented on the Incidental datasheet. “Fly-overs” do not go on the BBSA Detections datasheet.
- **Birds flying out of point:** If you observe BBSA flying out of the point, measure the distance between the point center (where you are standing) and where the birds flew from the ground. This information is recorded on the BBSA Detection Data sheet.
- Use binoculars to detect BBSA, not spotting scope. Spotting scope is used to verify species identification.
- Spend 5 minutes at the point scanning the quadrants for BBSA. Observers are to “get a snapshot” of the BBSA that were in the point when they arrived.

3.2 Detailed Instructions for the BBSA Detections Datasheet

1. At the start of each route, record: Route Number, Observer name(s), Date, and Start Time.
2. Circle yards or meters for the units that are reported by your rangefinder.
3. For every survey point, record the Point Number, even if there are no BBSA present. If there are no BBSA present, record 0 in the column “# BBSA in flock” (see Appendix for example data sheet).
4. Search each quadrant around the point for a 360° search. Search for at least 5 minutes per point for a standardized effort, even when it appears that no birds are present.
5. When BBSA are found, record the Point # and the quadrant where the birds are located.
6. Record the number of birds under “# of BBSA in the flock.”
 - a. A single bird is recorded with flock size = 1.
 - b. Count precisely the number of birds in each flock. If the flock is very large or moves away and you have to estimate the number of birds, please record that it is an estimate rather than actual count with a comment on the datasheet.
7. Record the distance to individual birds and flocks of BBSA:
 - a. When there are lone individuals, record the distance to each bird on a separate row on the datasheet.
 - b. When there are flocks of birds, record the distance to the center of the flock with each flock on a separate row on the datasheet.
 - c. Remember, accurate distance measurements (rangefinder) for birds at close range, before any movement, are most important for unbiased density estimates.
 - d. There is no limit to the distance searched when looking for BBSA but only use binoculars to locate BBSA (not a spotting scope). Record every bird or flock that you detect.
8. For each BBSA, or flock of birds, record the habitat conditions where the bird or flock is standing by marking an “X” in the appropriate columns. There are three habitat variables we are describing: habitat type, soil moisture and vegetation height. Definitions of these habitat variables are in Appendix 2.
 - a. For every individual BBSA and every BBSA flock, record the habitat type, soil moisture, and vegetation height found within 1 meter of the feet of the bird(s). These data are referred to in our project as the “micro-habitat” data. Similar habitat data (habitat type, moisture, and vegetation height) are also documented within each quadrant; quadrant data are recorded on the Point-Quadrant Habitat datasheet (see below).
 - b. If there is a group of birds using multiple micro-habitats, then document them as multiple flocks with a distance measurement to the center of each flock and different micro-habitats.
9. The goal is to “get a snapshot” of the BBSA that were at the point when the observer arrived. Do not record BBSA that fly into the point after you arrive (i.e., BBSA that fly into the point at 4.5 minutes after you arrive). BBSA that “fly in” to the point after the start of the survey should be recorded on the Incidental Datasheet.
10. At the end of route, record End Time and review datasheet for legibility and add any additional comments on the back of the sheet.
11. Please make sure there is a row with a Point # for every point that you surveyed, even the ones with no BBSA – record Point # and 0 for “number of birds in flock” if there were no birds at the point.

4.0 Instructions for the Habitat Datasheet (“macro-habitat” data)

4.1 General Instructions for the Habitat Datasheet (Habitat of Each Quadrant)

- **Latitude and Longitude for survey points:** The Point-Quadrant Habitat datasheet is the only place where the Latitude and Longitude for the survey points are recorded.

- It is important to record the lat-long of each point that is visited, even if you have used a GPS or similar device to direct you to the point. This is especially important when the point has been moved to a new location.
- The latitude and longitude of the point will determine the landscape-scale data that is associated with the survey point.
- In the space provided on data sheets, record if you are using a smart phone or GPS unit to obtain lat/long data.
- If using gps unit please set it to use WGS 84 “datum.” Some observers use smart phones (which use WGS 84 datum); to be consistent among observers we are all using WGS 84 datum. If you cannot switch to WGS 84 datum or you forgot to select it, record the datum you used on datasheet.
- It is important to record lat-long in decimal degrees with at least 5 decimal places to accurately locate points in a GIS analysis. On gps unit: position format- hddd.ddddd
- **Establishing quadrants around the survey point:** The area around the survey point is visually divided into quadrants (right front, right rear, left front, and left rear) to facilitate data collection and habitat mapping.
 - The road itself is the axis to determine “left” and “right”. Use the suggested route or direction of travel to the survey point (found in the KML file and PDF map) to determine which way to face, that is, “front” and “rear”. Face in the direction of the suggested roadway to the point and then you can visualize “left, right, front, and rear.”
- For the point-quadrant habitat data, record the dominant habitat type out to 400 m. When searching for BBSA there is no limit to the search distance, but when assessing the dominant habitat type in each quadrant, limit your assessment to 400 m.

4.2 Detailed Instructions for the Point-Quadrant Habitat Datasheet

1. At the top of the Point-Quadrant Habitat datasheet record the route number, observer name(s), and date (see example data sheet in Appendix).
2. Record each quadrant as either “RF” for right front, “RR” for right rear, “LF” for left front, and “LR” for left rear.
3. For each survey point, there are 4 rows to complete (one row for each quadrant). You will document the habitat type (i.e, rice, turf farm, rangeland), soil moisture and vegetation height of each quadrant. In the data sheet you will put an “X” in the appropriate columns. See the definitions for the habitat codes in Appendix 2 “Habitat Codes.”

5.0 Instructions for the Incidental Datasheet

- The incidental datasheet is optional but can be used to record
 - BBSA that are detected between survey points (en route).
 - BBSA that are detected as “flyovers” while at survey points; birds that do not land in sight during a point count survey are not included in the Detections datasheet, they are recorded as incidental observations.
 - Other shorebirds of interest.
- The latitude and longitude of BBSAs detected away from survey points will not only allow us to map the locations of all birds detected during the survey period, but also may be used to design future monitoring efforts.

- We are not collecting distance data for these incidental observations, only lat-longs. These data will not be used in our distance sampling analysis to estimate population size but are helpful in other analysis.
- If using gps unit please set it to use WGS 84 “datum” to be consistent among observers (some use smart phones which use WGS 84 datum). If you cannot switch to WGS 84 datum or you forgot to select it, record the datum you used on datasheet.
- These data are optional; our first priority is surveying the selected points and collecting accurate distance sampling data.
- If you are recording incidental data while at a survey point, it is not necessary to record the latitude and longitude on the Incidental datasheet; simply record the Point #.

6.0 Support and Communication

1. The overall project point of contact is Kelli Stone.
 - a. All survey logistics (range-finders, etc), questions about protocol (even when you are in the field), survey schedule (which route you are doing) or if you can't complete your survey:
 - b. If you can't complete your survey, contact Kelli ASAP so she can find an alternate observer
 - c. After completing your survey text, call or email Kelli your name, survey route and points you completed (and date completed).
 - d. Kelli Stone, call/text: 505-239-6934 kelli_stone@fws.gov
2. Route and GPS Support:
 - a. Need another copy of KML, pdf of map, questions about GPS or problem with your routes:
 - b. Notify Kammie ASAP if you had to move a point on your route (email her the new lat/long of Route and point #).
 - c. Kammie Kruse, 505-248-6875 (M-F), kammie_kruse@fws.gov Monday – Friday. Please try and contact her during the week, but she will try and be available on weekends on her personal cell 303-233-0305
 - d. The back-up person - Kelli Stone

7.0 Data Submission

- Ideally, we would really appreciate it if you could enter your data into Excel spreadsheet.
- LaReesa Wolfenbarger will email the excel spreadsheet template to observers with directions on entering data.
- Save your field sheets! At the end of the season (and after you have either entered your data or made copies of the data sheets) send the original field sheets to LaReesa Wolfenbarger at lwolfenbarger@unomaha.edu or UNO Dept. of Biology, Omaha, NE 68182-0040.

8.0 Stipend

- Stipends are available to the “volunteer” observers, which are defined as “non-staff biologist and/or staff biologist conducting survey in their own vehicle and on their own time.” Talk with Kelli if you need clarification.
- LaReesa Wolfenbarger will provide information on how to submit your invoice for reimbursement. Meanwhile please keep track of the routes you conducted and the dates you conducted surveys.

Appendix 1: GPS Support

GPS Support **Buff-breasted Sandpiper Surveys 2017** **By Kammie Kruse (USFWS – Migratory Birds Region 2)** *Updated April 3, 2018*

➤ **For Questions/Support: Kammie Kruse, M-F: 505-248-6875 or kammie_kruse@fws.gov**

Android phone **Accessing “KML” route files**

To open in Google **Maps** (*you will need to have a Google account*):

1. Need to use laptop/desktop to begin process. Open Google Maps on your laptop/desktop. If you are not already signed in please do so (sign-in is located on the Upper Right).
2. Click on the 3 horizontal lines at the left side of search bar:
3. Click on the “Your Places” link, then the Maps link, and then click on Create Map (link at bottom of column).
4. Create a new map (click in box where it says untitled map) and name it, select the “Import” button, and then import the KML file into that map from wherever you saved it.
5. After you have saved the map you can open **Google Maps** on your device (need to be signed in here too).
6. Choose the “Layers” button on the upper left (3 lines like Step 2). Then open "Your Places", Map Link and select the map you created on your desktop.
7. Your points will open up in **Google Map**
8. You will need to have internet access in the field to see the points>
9. You will need to do this for EACH one of your routes.

OR

To see your points in Google **Earth**:

1. On your Android device, open the Google Earth app.
2. From the left-hand menu, tap Google Drive. If prompted, sign in to your Google Account.
3. In Google Drive, find and tap the KML file in the left panel.
4. Turn visibility on or off to see the layer.

I think viewing the points in Google Maps is easier to see and use. You can turn on or off the satellite image as needed which you can't do in Google Earth. *Plus it will give you directions to your next point when you select it.*

iPhone **Accessing “KML” route files**

➤ **For Questions/Support: Kammie Kruse, M-F: 505-248-6875 or kammie_kruse@fws.gov**

To open in Google **Maps** (*you will need to have a Google account*):

1. Need to use laptop/desktop to begin process. Open Google Maps on your laptop/desktop. If you are not already signed in please do so (sign-in is located on the Upper Right).
2. Click on the 3 horizontal lines at the left side of search bar:
3. Click on the “Your Places” link, then the Maps link, and then click on Create Map (link at bottom of column)
4. Create a new map (click in box where it says untitled map) and name it, select the “Import” button, and then import the KML file into that map from wherever you saved it.
5. After you have saved the map you can open **Google Maps** on your device (need to be signed in here too).
6. Choose the “Layers” button on the upper left (3 lines like Step 2). *If you have not signed in then this is where you do it at the top of the screen. Then open "Your Places", “Map” button on right and select the map you created on your desktop.*
7. Your points will open up in **Google Map**.
8. You will need to have internet access in the field to see the points.
9. You will need to do this for EACH one of your routes

OR

To see your points in Google Earth:

1. Google Earth app needs to be downloaded on your iPhone.
2. Email kml file to yourself and open in the IOS mail app (*or just open email sent from Kammie directly in your IOS mail App*)
3. *Press on kml file (not tap because that will bring up a text file) and a menu will popup. In that menu there should be an option to open with Google Earth*
4. Points will now show up in Google earth
5. The points will not save there so you will have to open them from email every time you want to see them

I think viewing the points in Google Maps is easier to see and use. You can turn on or off the satellite image as needed which you can't do in Google Earth. *Plus it will give you directions to your next point when you select it.*

GPS Accessing “KML” route files

➤ **For Questions/Support: Kammie Kruse, M-F: 505-248-6875 or kammie_kruse@fws.gov**

For those using GPS units you will have to convert the KML files to a file type that your GPS can read.

1. Open free KML to GPX converter tool on this website: <https://kml2gpx.com/>
2. Select KML file to convert, click Convert button. Once it is done it will give you an option to download new GPX file. Save to your computer (make sure you know where it is saving).
3. Do this for each route.
4. Since there are many different GPS units out there you will need to use your units specific directions to get the GPX files uploaded to your unit and viewable for field use
5. **Please set your GPS to “WGS 84” datum.**

To Obtain Lat/Long points at actual stops

Your safety while conducting the survey is our **1st priority**. In developing our random locations not all of the points will be in a safe place for you to pull off the road (construction activities, etc). So please find the closest safe point for you to conduct the survey. Write down the coordinates for where you stop for each point, this is especially important for those stops you had to move. If you moved a point make a note on the data form that it was moved and why. We will then input those coordinates as the new location for proceeding years and for our analysis.

Android Phone

1. In Google Map App, click on the white circle to zoom into your location on the map.
2. Then press on blue dot and Lat/Longs should appear in white bar at top.

iPhone

1. You will need to open the iPhone Map App (**not Google Maps**).
2. Click on the Blue dot and at the bottom “My location” should pop up
3. Scroll down and the Latitude and Longitude should be listed

Appendix 2: Habitat Codes and Support (Contact Information for Project Assistance)

BBSA Surveys, Spring 2018. Definitions of Habitat Variables, Wind Speed, Sky Conditions (all codes used on data sheets). Use definitions below when describing the DOMINANT habitat within each quadrant of each point and when describing the habitat BBSA are in when observed. (3/17/2018)	
QUADRANTS	
LF LEFT FRONT LR LEFT REAR RF RIGHT FRONT RR RIGHT REAR	Use the road as an axis. Use pdf map of suggested route and face in the direction of the suggested path to the point. Then you can visualize “front, left, right, and back.”
DISTANCE	LAT & LONG
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Distance to center of BBSA flock at 1st sighting before movement. ▪ Record distance in meters or note otherwise. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Latitude and longitude where you collected data ▪ Record in decimal degrees (at least 5 decimal places).

HABITAT CATEGORY	DESCRIPTION FOR 2018
Turf (S) - species of sod is "St. Augustine"	Fat, glossy/waxy leaf. Enter "S" in Turf/Sod column in datasheet
Turf (B) - species of sod is "Bermuda Grass"	Thin, wispy leaf. Enter "B" in Turf/Sod column on datasheet
Turf farm (U) - species of sod unknown	Enter "U" in Turf/Sod column on datasheet
Rice	Rice production area; active or idle.
Pasture/Grassland	Dominated by grasses, herbaceous vegetation, introduced or domesticated forage species. May receive periodic renovation and/or cultural treatments, such as tillage, fertilization, mowing, weed control, and may be irrigated. Not in rotation with crops. Land may be used for the production of grazing animals.
Soybean	Soybean: 3 leaflets
Corn	Corn and sorghum difficult to distinguish in early stages. Check both if unsure.
Sorghum	Corn and sorghum difficult to distinguish in early stages. Check both if unsure.
Cotton	Cotton: leaves
Building	Check if there is a building within 500 m of point
Sugarcane	
Unidentified row crop	Cultivated crop (row crop - species unknown)
Herbaceous Wetlands	Emergent, non-woody wetlands
Aquaculture	crawfish, catfish ponds
Open Water	

HABITAT CATEGORY (cont.)	DESCRIPTION FOR 2018
Developed/open space	Areas with a mixture of developed and open space but mostly vegetation in the form of lawn grasses. Impervious surfaces account for <20% of cover. Large-lot single family housing unit, parks, golf courses, vegetation planted in developed settings for recreation erosion control or aesthetics.
Building present?	Check if there is a building within 400 m of point

SOIL MOISTURE	
Dry	Soil is dry
Moist	Soil is moist; no surface water present.
Wet	Water on soil surface, standing water present.

VEGETATION HEIGHT
Bare Ground (no vegetation)
Vegetation height <1" (vegetation present but <1")
Vegetation height 1-4"
Vegetation height 4-8"
Vegetation height > 8 inches (taller than BBSA)

WIND SPEED (BEAUFORT SCALE)	
0 = smoke rises vertically (< 1 mph)	
1 = wind direction shown by smoke drift but not wind vanes (1-3 mph)	
2 = wind felt on face; leaves rustle; wind vanes moved by wind (4-7 mph)	
3 = leaves, small twigs in constant motion (8-12 mph)	
4 = dust rises; small branches move (13-18 mph)	
5 = small trees in leaf begin to sway (19-24 mph)	
SKY CONDITIONS	
0 = clear or few clouds	4 = fog or smoke
1 = partly cloudy or variable	5 = drizzle
2 = cloudy or overcast	8 = showers

SUPPORT AND COMMUNICATION	
Kelli Stone – Main point of contact. Survey schedule, when you have completed your survey, assistance with protocol, accessing data sheets, etc.	Call/text: 505-239-6934 (work cell) or kelli_stone@fws.gov
Kammie Kruse - KML file of survey routes and GPS Support (back up person – Kelli).	M-F: Office: 505-248-6875 kammie_kruse@fws.gov. Please contact her during the week, but she will try to be available on weekends: 303-233-0305.

Appendix 3: Example Completed Datasheets

BBSA Detection Datasheet				2018 BBSA Gulf Coast Surveys																				
Observer: <i>L. GRISCOM</i>				Temp (F): <i>70</i>				Sky: <i>1</i>				Wind: <i>0</i>												
Route #: <i>5</i>		Circle distance unit: <u>yards</u> OR meters																						
Date: <i>4/27/2018</i>																								
Start: <i>7:15</i>		Micro-habitat within 1 m of flock or individual																						
End: <i>13:30</i>																								
Point #	Quad-rant	# of BBSA in flock	Distance to flock center or individual bird	HABITAT											SOIL			VEG. HT.						
				Turf/Sod (S or B or U)	Rice	Pasture/Grassland	Soybeans	Corn	Sorghum	Cotton	Sugarcane	Unidentified crop	Herbaceous Wetlands	Aquaculture	Open Water	Developed/open space	Other (Describe)	Building present?	Dry	Moist	Wet (surface water)	bare ground	<1"	1-4"
<i>1</i>	<i>—</i>	<i>0</i>	<i>—</i>																					
<i>2</i>	<i>LF</i>	<i>1</i>	<i>57</i>	<i>B</i>														<i>X</i>					<i>X</i>	
<i>2</i>	<i>LF</i>	<i>13</i>	<i>74</i>	<i>B</i>														<i>X</i>					<i>X</i>	
<i>2</i>	<i>RF</i>	<i>6</i>	<i>121</i>	<i>B</i>	<i>X</i>													<i>X</i>						<i>X</i>
<i>3</i>	<i>—</i>	<i>0</i>	<i>—</i>																					
<i>4</i>	<i>—</i>	<i>0</i>	<i>—</i>																					
<i>5</i>	<i>—</i>	<i>0</i>	<i>—</i>																					
<i>6</i>	<i>—</i>	<i>0</i>	<i>—</i>																					
<i>7</i>	<i>—</i>	<i>0</i>	<i>—</i>																					
<i>8</i>	<i>—</i>	<i>0</i>	<i>—</i>																					
<i>9</i>	<i>LR</i>	<i>1</i>	<i>56</i>															<i>X</i>				<i>X</i>		
<i>9</i>	<i>LR</i>	<i>1</i>	<i>63</i>															<i>X</i>				<i>X</i>		
<i>9</i>	<i>LR</i>	<i>1</i>	<i>71</i>															<i>X</i>				<i>X</i>		
<i>10</i>	<i>—</i>	<i>0</i>	<i>—</i>																					
<i>11</i>	<i>—</i>	<i>0</i>	<i>—</i>																					
<i>12</i>	<i>RF</i>	<i>1</i>	<i>63</i>						<i>X</i>									<i>X</i>					<i>X</i>	
<i>12</i>	<i>RF</i>	<i>17</i>	<i>125</i>						<i>X</i>									<i>X</i>					<i>X</i>	
<i>13</i>	<i>—</i>	<i>0</i>	<i>—</i>																					
<i>14</i>	<i>—</i>	<i>0</i>	<i>—</i>																					
<i>15</i>	<i>—</i>	<i>0</i>	<i>—</i>																					
<i>16</i>	<i>RR</i>	<i>8</i>	<i>22</i>	<i>B</i>														<i>X</i>				<i>X</i>		
<i>16</i>	<i>RR</i>	<i>4</i>	<i>63</i>	<i>B</i>														<i>X</i>				<i>X</i>		
<i>16</i>	<i>RR</i>	<i>4</i>	<i>250</i>	<i>B</i>															<i>X</i>			<i>X</i>		
<i>16</i>	<i>LF</i>	<i>8</i>	<i>80</i>	<i>B</i>														<i>X</i>				<i>X</i>		
<i>16</i>	<i>LF</i>	<i>3</i>	<i>88</i>	<i>B</i>														<i>X</i>				<i>X</i>		

Send data file to lwolfenbarger@unomaha.edu and data sheet to: L. Wolfenbarger; UNO Dept of Biology, Omaha, NE 68182-0040

APPENDIX 4. Tables Comparing Buff-Breasted Sandpiper (BBSA) and Other Shorebird Species Common in Upland Habitats (PESA = Pectoral Sandpiper, AGPL = American Golden Plover, and UPSA = Upland Sandpiper).

SPECIES COMPARISON				
	BBSA	PESA	AGPL	UPSA
OVERALL APPEARANCE	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Buffy colored • Medium size 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Medium sized • Gray • Conspicuous contrast between streaked breast & white belly. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Plump, light brown, • Erect posture 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Large, long necked shorebird • Small head
EYE	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Dark eye on pale buff face 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Dark eye on brown face • White eye stripes 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Dark eye on gray face • Weak eye stripes 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Dark eye on light gray face
HEAD SHAPE	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Bill same length as head 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Bill longer than head 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Black stubby bill shorter than head 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Long neck • Yellow & black bill longer than head
LEG COLOR	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Yellow Orange 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Orange 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Black 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Yellow

SPECIES COMPARISON				
	BBSA	AGPL	UPSA	PESA
BEHAVIOR	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • High stepping pigeon-like gait, • Seldom staying at one site to peck 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Takes several quick steps then pause to look for food 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Ambling gait, stops for occasional peck • Often in small groups 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Does not amble • Methodical probing of substrate
HABITAT	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Agricultural fields, bare ground, short grass, and tall sparse forbs on dry and moist sites • Usually short vegetation 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Same as BBSA • Less prone to use wetlands 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Bare ground, short grass and sparse tall grass. • Not common in wetlands 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Same as BBSA except more frequent on wet sites

